

The Revolutionary Political Tussle Of Colonial India: An Epitome Of Buxa Detention Camp

Subhamay Dutta

Ph.D. Research Scholar

Department of History

Cooch Behar Panchanan Barma University

Cooch Behar, West Bengal

Abstract: The revolutionary movement had links to Bengal and the national political system. The Indian freedom struggle became a mass movement in 1915, after the joining of M.K Gandhi. At the same time, militant nationalist forces regained their old form. Bengal politics was quite advanced and opposed Gandhi's objectives. The Bengal revolutionaries questioned Gandhi's views. The organisation of the Bengal Congress Committee was divided into many fragmented. Furthermore, the Bengal province played an important part in ultranationalist politics. The British government passed the Bengal Criminal Law Amendment Act in 1930. Many detention camps were created quickly, including three in Bengal (Buxa, Hijli, and Berhampur) and the Deoli detention camp in Rajasthan. However, the Buxa detention camp's detainees played a significant role in the aspect of political basis. The Buxa detention camp was included as a special episode of Bengal politics in these extracts. The provincial congress committee election and Calcutta municipal corporation election were a historical dimension of congress and revolutionary politics.

Keywords: Detention Camps, Detainees, BCLA 1930, Buxa Camp, Council election

Introduction In the phase of the Nationalist movement in India, all the secret organizations of Bengal were engaged in national politics. In 1905 the era of the Swadeshi movement the nationalist struggle gained an optimum role. The Sedition Committee Report (1918) mentioned that the root of the revolution in the thought by Narendranath Datta also known as Swami Vivekananda. The revolutionary ideas were promoted in the field of Bengal politics. Colonial perspectives, armed revolutionary struggle remarked by terroristic nature. On the other hand, Rowlatt's Act Committee referred to the 'revolutionary' word in various modes. Eminent author Judith Brown, Valentine Chirol, Sidney Rowlatt, and Mr. J.C Ker I.C.S used the word 'terrorist'. The national movement got impetus in 1915 after the participation of M.K Gandhi. 'The Future of Indian Politics' written by Manabendra Nath Roy, he expresses a path for the revolutionary Nationalist forces; points out the causes of the decline of bourgeois Nationalism; exposes the tendency of compromise underneath the verbal

radicalism of the upper middle class; and indicates the historical necessity for the fight for freedom. The decline of bourgeois Nationalism has given a new impetus to terrorist organizations.

The Government implemented repressive laws, the Indian Criminal Law Amendment Act XIV of 1908 was passed on 11th December. In January 1909, Swadesh Bandhab Samiti (Bakharganj), Suhrid Samiti (Mymensingh), Anushilan Samiti (Dacca) Brati Samiti (Faridpur), and Sadhana Samiti from Mymensingh. Pulin Bihari Das, the leader of Dacca Anushilan Samiti, was deported together with eight other individuals in November 1908, following Regulation III of 1818. The Bengal Secret group was mostly divided into four units: I. Anushilan Samiti, II. B.V. group, Shri Sangha, III. Jugantar Party, and IV. Revolt Party. The revolt party was initiated by Satcouri Banerjee

'Constraints in Bengal Politics, 1921-1941, Gandhian Leadership' by Gitashree Bandyopadhyay, the book examines the clash between Bengal and National politics. Mahatma Gandhi faced ideological opposition in Bengal, the politically most advanced province. There were occasions when the conflict involved parties or groupings. The parties involved were the communists, communal Muslims, and revolutionaries. C.R. Das and Subhas Ch. Bose were two individuals whose beliefs and approaches contradict Gandhi's. The historical explanation of the nationalist movement in India was described by Judith Brown's book '*Modern India: The Origins of an Asian Democracy.*' (1985). The revolutionary members backed both Chittaranjan Das and Subhas Chandra Bose on political grounds. Rabindranath Tagore noticed it was a moral decline, notwithstanding Gandhi's strong opposition to their actions. V.L. Lenin resisted the terrorist movement in 1907 to gain independence. However, Lenin believed that only a mass revolution could overthrow the capitalist class.

M. K Gandhi's followers won in the Bengal Provincial Congress Committee and the Gaya Congress Session; consequently, the congress was split into two phases: the pro-changer and the no-changer. Chittaranjan Das left Congress to form the Congress-khilafat Swaraj Party on January 1, 1923, with Motilal Nehru. C.R. Das assisted the Jugantar Party in these cases. In the Bengal Provincial Congress Committee, Bhupati Majumdar, Satyen Mitra, Bipin Ganguly, Gopen Roy, Amarendra Chatterjee, and Manoranjan Gupta participate. Interestingly all were detained in Buxa camp Under BCLA 1930. Amarendra Chatterjee, Upen Banerjee, Bipin Ganguly, and Satyen Mitra were placed in the All-India Congress Committee. Satyen Mitra and Subhas Ch. Bose was selected as secretary of the Swarajya Party.

Particularly, C.R. Das and Subhas Chandra Bose were supported by the Jugantar group and sympathized with the revolutionaries. But Mr. Gandhi led the nation towards a non-violent revolution against imperialism. S.C. Bose began his political career by joining Gandhi's forces. S.C. Bose denied Gandhian politics, another way C.R. Das founded the Swarajya Party after first opposing Gandhian thought. Consequently, the Bengal revolutionaries believed in achieving independence with military actions. They established a second front and started violent actions alongside the Congress-led non-violent agenda. The members of revolutionary parties in Bengal were essential to the expansion and advancement of Swarajist power. This played a part in the

resurgence of the revolutionary movement, which in the 1920s and 1930s presented a serious threat to non-violence—one of the cornerstones of Gandhian ideas.

After the demise of C.R Das, The Bengal Provincial Congress Committee (BPCC) divided into two fighting groups behind S. C. Bose and J. M. Sengupta. Even Gandhi's call for civil disobedience failed to unite the ranks of the Bengal Congress.

The nation stood with the revolutionaries and held them in the highest regard during these arms races. The nation backed distinctly the revolutionaries, but they were also generous in providing financial backing. The government called it a '*revolutionary mentality*'. In 1920, the Indian National Congress approved a revolutionary programme of action incorporating all facets of society for the first time. After the royal proclamation of 1919, all those who had been detained under the Defence of India Act were released and the amnesty was extended gradually to most of the leaders of the revolutionary movement—no evidence of the connection to Congress.

The revolutionaries respected the eminent barrister C.R. Das, who also gave the program his approval under tight deadlines. In 1921, the liberated revolutionaries arrived here and offered to become members of Congress. Though they were unaware of it, Bengalis were aware of Gandhi's Congress propaganda. Bengal leaders who refused to follow the ideas, they wanted to be changed, including C.R Das and Bipin Chandra Pal, lost the congress session in Calcutta. The party of ex-detainees was escorted to Nagpur by C.R. Das to rescind or revise the resolution from September. Under the direction of Srish Chandra Chatterjee, some 300 former detainees, and ex-convicts of the Dacca Anushilan samiti travelled to Nagpur in support of C.R. Das, according to the authorities.

The authorities further estimated that C.R Das paid the delegates from Bengal and Assam out of his pocket, estimating Rs. 36,000. Das agreed to a year of non-violent resistance and asked revolutionaries to halt their armed uprising plan in Gandhi's promised year of Swaraj. Six representatives of the Jugantar party met Gandhi at the Congress camp in Nagpur on a chilly December midnight. At Barishal Aswini Kumar Dutta's leadership, Swadesh Bandhab Samiti took on the role and powers of a de facto shadow government, overseeing Swadeshi, national education, Hindu-Muslim unity in society, arbitration courts, vigilance corps, and other related matters. Gandhi's agenda excluded several other items, such as the establishment of a shadow government. Nevertheless, the revolutionaries saw in Gandhi's programme the potential for increased public engagement and mass communication in opposing the bureaucracy, and as a result, they all heeded Gandhi's call, which was relayed by Chittaranjan Das.

The idea that the movement would give the disgruntled workers new hope was the only thing that led a large number of revolutionaries to join Gandhi's initiatives. Dinesh Dasgupta, Satyen Mitra, and Basanta Kumar Majumder are ex-detainees. It was chosen to be the assistant secretary, and Jugantar leader Arun Chandra Guha was assigned to the BPCC as a clerk. Instead of entering the Congress out of respect for Gandhi's nonviolence, they did so as a fresh arena for activity. According to police reports from Bengaluru in January

1921, attempts were made to organize the Revolutionary Party, particularly in Faridpur. Purna Das, the former detainee, was attempting to establish a covert group to support the non-cooperation movement there. Additionally, there have been reports of increasing activity from ex-detenus and freed state detenus across the province. The revolutionaries were able to appoint new members to the Congress by reforming and reorganizing their party. After the foundation of the Swaraj Party maintained a formal relationship between the bourgeoisie and the people as a whole by making the interests of native capital the basis of its 'national demand.' Now that the rapprochement with imperialism is practically complete, the bourgeoisie does not need the superficial political radicalism of the middle-class intellectuals. Therefore, the Right Wing of the Swaraj Party, which consciously represents capitalist interests, declares in favour of political peace and breaks away to join the Liberal ranks. The majority of the Swaraj Party, which loudly reiterates their determination to keep up the parliamentary opposition, has gradually tempered their political demands to small measures of administrative reform. The rise of the Swaraj Party in 1923 indicated a move to the Right. Those elements of the National Congress which had all along been opposed to the boycott of reforms and were against committing the Nationalist movement to revolutionary mass action, were the organisers of the Swaraj Party. The Swaraj Party does not stand for a democratic revolution, as its program and record of activities indicate. The programme of the Swaraj party brought the Nationalist movement back to its bourgeois (and even feudal) basis which had been somewhat lost sight of in the hectic days of 1920-21. The Swaraj Party replaced revolutionary mass action with parliament obstruction as the tactics of Nationalist politics.

After the revolutionaries joined, C.R Das was able to obtain a majority in the BPCC with their assistance. By the middle of 1923, they had established themselves as the main party in the AICC. Revolutionary groups were deeply involved in the Swarajya Party. The Swarajya Party was resolved to see the Regulation III Act repealed. According to the IB, the revolutionaries received Rs. 15,000 from the Swaraj party budget, with a further Rs. 25,000 promised between 1923 and 1924. Jugantar and Anushilan, the two main groups, had independently developed their plans of action. The Jugantar openly rebelled against the non-violent path. Arun Ch. Guha and Harikumar Chakraborty started a weekly called '*Swadhinata*', which quickly turned into a potent medium for violence in their quest to dispel any illusions regarding the effectiveness of nonviolence. The Revolting Group was a new political party founded by Santosh Mitra, Ganesh Ghosh, Jatin Das, and Satish Ch. Pakrashi.

Council election:

All the detainees were released from various jails then they joined a national movement, Mr. C.R Das was supported by the terrorists without their help he could not have won the council election. It is known that the leader of the Swarajya party was aware that his terrorist allies were engaged in a criminal conspiracy. Sirajganj Congress conference Mr. C.R Das with the help of his terrorist supporters succeeded in passing his Hindu-Muslim pact resolution. There was no scope for his connivance for their support which was essential to his success in elections. The government arrested most of the leaders in Regulation III, 1818 all were members of the Swarajya party.

The most interesting issue, both parties in Calcutta were at the same places' headquarters. In 1924 the terrorist members of the Swarajya party supported the candidature of Mr. Subhas Chandra Bose as the CEO of the corporation and it is noteworthy that after his appointment to that post CEO Subhas Chandra Bose, who employed a large number of Jugantar revolutionaries and ex-detenus under the Calcutta corporation, was detained under Regulation III of 1818. Many Revolutionary terrorists among whom there were also many congress workers were arrested. Swarajya party claims govt. of deliberately attacking not the terrorists but the Swarajists, many meetings were organized all over Bengal under the auspicious of the Bengal Provincial Congress committee. Ex-detenus or political ex-prisoners were office bearers of the Bengal Provincial Congress Committee and 21 revolutionaries or sympathizers were elected to the all-India Congress committee. According to reports by British Intelligence Chittaranjan Das, the Swarajya Party withdrew its support if the Jugantar Party instigated any violence and Mr. C.R Das was against terrorism.

Mr. Jatindra Mohan Sengupta and his successors followed the same course of action as the terrorists after C.R. Das passed away in June 1925, they also realized that the Swarajya party could not win elections for council or municipal bodies without their assistance. Many terrorists participated actively in the 1930 civil disobedience movement and were imprisoned for their anti-British activities. Members of the Dacca Anushilan Samiti backed J.M. Sengupta, whereas members of the Jugantar party backed Subhas Ch. Bose and his party. Two instances show how the terrorist regarded their connection with the congress. In June 1931 certain detainees had been present at a meeting at the Buxa detention Camp which a resolution in support of Jatindra Mohan Sengupta's revolt against the Bengal provincial congress committee was passed. This enraged the detenus of the Jugantar party in the camp who met in July and drew up a resolution in reply. They forwarded this resolution to the proper authority for transmission to 'The Advance' newspapers. The detenus of Buxa camp assembled in this public meeting emphatically protested against and condemned the action of the editor of the advance publishing in its issue of the 20 June 1931 an utterly false and mischievous report about a meeting held in this camp on 16 June 1931, alleged to be attended amongst others by sites.

Secretary of State for India, Samuel John Gurney Hoare, stated that there is also evidence in plenty that in the province of Bengal leaders of the congress particularly the left-hand leaders are in close contact with the terroristic movement but the govt. has not been able to prove the existence of such a party either allied with the Congress or separated from the Congress organization.

Mainly Bengal, Panjab, and Madras inmates came to Andaman jail. Already they believe in communism. On the other hand, many nationalist revolutionaries protested the communism. More significantly, On April 26, 1935, 'Communist consolidation' was founded at the Andaman Cellular Jail secretly. On 1st May 1935, 'Communist consolidation' lit up a new sphere in political history. However, in 1936, it was depicted that the spread of communist ideas was an important factor in the future policy of terrorists. The infusion of communist doctrines into the terrorist ranks had been noticeable since the Hindustan socialist republican army. Including Buxa Fort, most of the detainees in detention camps in recent years have been intensively studying communism and socialism.

The Chittagong group was very organized in Andaman cellular jail. On 25th July 1937, the prisoners started a hunger strike. On the first day, 200 prisoners were engaged in a hunger strike. Provincial election was finished therefore a little liberty came to many provinces. In the short span, numerous newspapers published the news of Andaman. Bengal was filled with political southing, poster banners, and a protest in the public gallery. Political activists and revolutionaries in India are being interned in jails and detention camps without any process of law. Political detenus from Buxa, Hijli, Deoli, Berhampur, Alipore, the Presidency jail, Dacca, Rajsahi, and Midnapore jails were particularly active in supporting Andaman prisoners. Within fifteen days of the agitation, the British administration was given a prominent role in rural or urban Bengal.

Issues of Releasing Detainees:

In the context of Detenus in Fazlul Haq government in Bengal, mentioned that Mr. Gandhi would arrive on the 10th or 11th and during his visit would try to induce govt. to release orders against Detenus. He requested H.M. Home to consider whether all the Detenus now village and home domicile could not be released before Mr. Gandhi's arrival he pointed out the difference between the Detenus and political prisoners and mentioned the distractibility of all units of the British govt. in India having a common policy in this matter. The seven congress provinces were releasing all prisoners and he thought it advisable that this govt. also should consider the desirability. Dangerous detainees' release should be gradual.

The Congress dominates the provinces, and Bengal Chief Minister A.K. Fazlul Haque intervened in Andaman affairs. However, this treatment was completely ineffective. The hunger strike among all detainees grew stronger with each passing day. After 22 days, Sharat Chandra Basu, a seasoned opposition party leader, posed questions to the Bengal province government in the Bengal legislative council. He said, '*What is the situation of the prisoners in Andaman?*' Dinesh Gupta and Sukendu Das have already perished as a result of their hunger strike. The Bengal government was unable to answer those queries. Following that, Gandhiji and Rabindranath became active in these concerns. After being unwell for 27 days, Rabindranath presided over a program. He vividly appealed '*Aaj ar Beshi Kotha Bolar Proyojon Nei, Amra Amader Ei Amulya Chele Guloke Andaman-e Nivrite Nivte Dite Parina, Eder Abilambe Firiye Ana Hok*'.

Andaman detainees were regularly receiving 10–15 telegrams. All revolutionaries have been requested to end their hunger strike. Several Congress chief ministers promised to back the revolutionary's demands. However, the Bengali administration was unable to accept all of the demands. As a result, all of the prisoners are continuing their hunger strike in support of the Bengali prisoners' demands. Already, the federal legislature has passed a resolution in support of Andaman detainees. Prisoners are particularly concentrating on two telegrams delivered by Gandhiji and Rabindranath. Muzaffar Ahmad and Bankim Mukherjee sent another telegram to Andaman Cellular Jail. They asked for an end to the hunger strike. Finally, the Bengal Assembly sent a message to the captives in which they agreed to the revolutionaries' demands. Finally, the government promoted the Andaman convicts to Division II rank. But there was no way to carry out that suggestion. Due to the lack of prison camps in Bengal province, During the time Mahatma Gandhi visited Bengal, He met with

political detainees in the Hijli and presidential jails. Following that, Gandhi visited Alipore jail. Prisoners are conversing with Gandhi. Congress-minded revolutionaries joined the national movement.

In January of 1938, numerous revolutionaries began a hunger strike in a cellular jail. All the Bengal jails issued a request to the British government. In 1938, many detainees were released from jails. Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, and Madras Congress ministers resigned. In this situation, the Bengal government released some detainees. 45 convicts are so dangerous that they are not freed. Bidhan Ch Roy, M.K. Gandhi, Rajendra Prasad, S.C. Basu, and Prafulla Ghosh visited the revolutionaries in various jails. After 38 days, the Muslim League mayor of Calcutta and Sharat Ch. Basu persuaded the revolutionaries to end their hunger strike.

Buxa camp: detainees and political genesis

Revolutionaries thought many revolutionary groups could not succeed in their attempts. Bengal Volunteer and the Revolting group had a deep relationship. Satya Gupta, Kiran Mukherjee, and Satcouri Banerjee Bhupen Dutta launched a new direct-action plan against the emperor. During the first half of 1930, secret societies carried out numerous revolutionary activities. Nikunja Sen, Rasamay Sur, Prafulla Dutta, Haridas Dutta, and Supati Roy participated in the direct-action plan. Ultimately, they all found themselves arrested and imprisoned in various detention camps. Hem Chandra Ghosh, a B.V. leader free from his incarnated life, travelled to Mumbai (erstwhile Bombay) with Subhas Ch. Bose on March 19, 1931. They began revoking Bhagat Singh's hanging order, and the Gandhi-Irwin accord was ultimately ineffective. In 1938, a Bengal volunteer participated in public politics under S.C. Bose. As a result, rumours of S.C. Bose's death shattered the national independence struggle's cohesiveness. B.V. and Shree Sangha leaders continued their work, believing that Netaji had not died owing to the plane crash. In 1943-1944, the Forward Bloc launched an impetus role on an all-India basis as a national movement.

In these conditions, B.V. and Shree Sangha were determined to dissolve every branch of secret societies and launch a new political wave with the Forward Bloc. Bengal Volunteers worked tirelessly to organise the Forward Bloc. Surprisingly, all secret societies were disbanded in the Buxa Fort detention camp with the support of B.V. and planned nationalist movements with an entirely new viewpoint. At the same time, Hem Chandra Ghosh, Lila Roy, and Anil Roy. Purna Ch. Das, Satya Gupta, Amalendu Dasgupta, Dwijen Das, Suren Sarkar, Deben De, Panna Mitra, Ashrafuddin Choudhury, Haren Ghosh, Rasamay Sur, Bhabesh Nandi, Bhupendra Nath Rakshit Roy, Panchanan Chakraborty, Phani Majumder, Rakhil Dutta, and Jatin Bhattacharjee were released from prison in 1946. Unfortunately, Hemchandra Ghosh returned from the Mymensingh conference; later, Hem Chandra's friends became involved with the revolutionary socialist party (RSP). Gradually, the Bengal nationalist movement was quickly slowed down.

Conclusion: The political battle in Bengal developed a historical dimension during the ultra-nationalist phase. The Bengali provinces were the primary place of origin for militant nationalism in some ways. Numerous nationalist groupings were involved in covert organisations—the primary conflict between revolutionaries' and Gandhi's political ideologies gained a new outlook in the history of modern India. The political tussles

lightened the Calcutta municipal corporation election and the council election. Specifically, C.R. Das, S.C. Bose, and J. M. Sengupta were supported by the detained revolutionaries. The Buxa, Hijli, and Berhampur detention camps are closely related in the field of political conflict between the two perspectives. Jugantar, Anushilan, and the small secret societies participated in both Bengal and national politics.

References:

1. Sedition Committee Report, 1918, President, The Hon'ble Mr. Justice Rowlat, Judge of the King's Bench Division of His Majesty's High Court of Justice. Calcutta, Superintendent Government Printing, India 1918
2. Roy, M.N, *The Future of Indian Politics*, R. Bishop Blomfield, London, p., 45
3. Sedition Committee, p.,40
4. Das, Nalini, *Swadhinata Sangrame Dwipantarar Bandi*, Manisa, Kolkata, 1974, p., 47
5. Bandyopadhyay, Gitashree '*Constraints in Bengal Politics, 1921-1941, Gandhian Leadership*', Sarat Book House, Kolkata, 1984, p., IX
6. Tripathi, Amalesh, *Swadhinata Sangrame Bharater Jatiya Congress, 1885-1947*, Ananda, Kolkata, Ashar, 1417, p., 76
7. Bandyopadhyay, Gitashree, '*Constraints in Bengal Politics, 1921-1941, Gandhian Leadership*', p., x.
8. Chatterji, Joya, *Bengal divided, Hindu communalism and partition, 1932-1947*, Cambridge University Press, 1994, p., 2
9. I.B, *Terrorism in Bengal: 1917-1936 Confidential*, 1937, p., 13,
10. Roy. M.N, *The Future of Indian Politics*, p., 45,
11. West Bengal State Archive, Home political file- 26/32 A Brief Note on the Alliance of Congress with Terrorism in Bengal, p.,2,
12. West Bengal State Archive, Home political file- 26/32, A Brief Note on the Alliance of Congress with Terrorism in Bengal
13. West Bengal State Archive, IB, Gopal Halder M.A.B.L. S/o Sita Kanta of Bhatgaon, Munshi Ganj Dacca & Noakhali Srinagar. 1932, 49/1932, 277/1932
14. West Bengal State Archive, IB file, Cabinet Papers 1.3.1938 meeting of the cabinet at writers building on 1.3.38 H.E.M presiding present – A. K Fazlul Haq
15. Rakshit Roy, Bhupendra Kishor, *Sabar Alokhye*, Radical Impression, Kolkata, 2018, p., 145